
SOCIAL MEDIA AND CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT WITH THE WAR AGAINST DRUG ABUSE

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Abstract

Drug and substance abuse are a growing health problem all over the world. Globally, 36 million people are estimated to suffer from drug use disorders with the adverse health consequences more severe and widespread than previously thought. In Nigeria, the drug problem portends great danger, with multiple public health concerns encompassing addiction and vulnerability to sundry drug use disorders and dependence. In fact, the United Nations Office on Drug and Crime (UNODC) in Nigeria reported in 2022 that around 14.4% (14.3 million) of people aged 15 and 64 years abuse drugs. This figure, then, was higher than the global average. In response, the Nigerian government launched the War Against Drug Abuse (WADA) and declared that drug abuse was deadlier than insurgency as it remains a catalyst for insurgency and destroys generations. Two agencies tasked with the responsibility of stemming the tide of drug abuse in Nigeria are the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) and the National Agency for Food Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC). Globally, citizen engagement in the fight against substance abuse is in vogue, and a variety of approaches intended to publicize the dangers of drug abuse and engender greater public advocacy participation are occurring worldwide. Scholars and policy makers have increasingly advocated engaging citizens more substantially in the fight and many anti-narcotic agencies believe such collaboration could prevent remote communities from turning into illicit drug dens. NDLEA and NAFDAC are tending to promote the drug war via the use of social media. In this study, we

relied on literature searches to determine the status of social media depth in Nigeria, and conducted a qualitative content analysis of the social media handles, accounts and pages of the NDLEA and NAFDAC, to ascertain the deployment or otherwise of social media by these organizations for the purpose of engaging with the public in the fight against drug abuse, using website interactive features, hyperlinks, audience traffic analytics, as well as video and sound click analytics, as units of analysis in gauging Nigerian anti narcotic agency-audience engagements. Social media hold great promise, but agency-public engagements, most times is frail. This paper calls on Nigerian anti-narcotic institutions to appraise the pragmatics of their public engagement and participation, in order to win the war against drug abuse.

Keywords: Social Media, Interaction, Citizen Engagement, Drug Abuse, Substance, Prevalence, Narcotics.

Introduction

The ubiquity of digital networking platforms or social media has revolutionized communication and the processes of information sharing. In fact, no technological innovation in media has impacted our lives in terms of speed and immediacy in the last two decades more than the social networks (Potter, 2013). Social media has been an incredible asset for connecting with friends and family, allowing us to stay in touch with those both near and far. It also gives us the ability to connect with people of similar interests, views, and experiences. From aviation to computing, predictive analytics, e-business intelligence, education, crime tracking, travel, information storage and retrieval, and everyday relationships – social media have changed our lives dramatically. These days, almost everyone has a social media account or two. Everywhere you turn, you find people head-on, really busy on their cell phones, whether they are on dates, in or at the movie. People just can't seem to pull themselves away from their phones.

We are in the era of social media and these tools will continue to shape our lives in primal ways: offering a potent platform for obtaining, generating and disseminating information, an avenue to learn and educate, and a forum to apprehend and interrogate new ideas, including knowledge about science, medicine and technology. In spite of the perceived benefits of social media, Romer and Moreno (2017, n p), however, note that they hold significant implications for drug abuse by “providing increased opportunities for both marketing and social transmission of risky products and behavior through exposure and favorable presentations of addictive substances, such as alcohol,

tobacco, and marijuana, as well as behaviors such as gambling, with teens, youths and young adults often the primate targets.”

The Australian Bureau of Statistics Service (2018, p. 3) buttressed the point when it noted that in the age of technology, social media and digital communication play a major role in drug misuse. “Ninety-eight percent of 15-17-year old Australian teenagers use the Internet, and the majority of these teenagers access it for social networking. As youths increasingly spend more time online, how does this affect their use of alcohol and other drugs? Social media exposes them to alcohol-related advertising and substance-related content from their peers. Social media posts from peers and other teenagers may glorify the use of alcohol and drugs, as it is often portrayed in a positive light”, (ABS, 2018). The study found a link between using the Internet for social interaction and past month drug use (alcohol, cannabis, vaping) amongst young adults.

In Nigeria, several studies have established a clear correlation between social media and drug abuse, and that the drug problem portends great danger, with multiple public health concerns encompassing addiction and vulnerability to sundry drug use disorders and dependence. In a report in the *Guardian* of May 10, 2023 entitled “Social Media and our Drug Problem” by Philemon Akwu, the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) reported that 40 percent of Nigerian youths, between 18 and 35, are deeply involved in the abuse of drugs, which it said was alarming. The agency said neither it nor the society could completely claim ignorance of how its young adults are being lured into drug abuse. It said social media was to blame, and remained the biggest influencer at that.

The pernicious influence of social media in our lives has been a growing concern to modern society. These days, the fear of social media is the beginning of wisdom. Unfortunately, social media is now seemingly an integral part of our lives. For teenagers, whether they are at home, work, in school, shopping with friends, or visiting family for the holidays, their eyes are frequently fixed on the screen of their mobile phones. The good part of this is that we are more connected to one another than ever before. The bad aspect is that social media connections are not the same as socialising in real life. When teenagers spend crazy amounts of time on social media, it can heighten the chances of negative influences coming through and touching their lives. Among those negative influences is drug abuse. In this time and age, social media is the biggest influencer on the disposition of youths: their fashion sense,

their taste in music, their lifestyle choices, and career paths. In this new social paradigm, celebrities have replaced parents as teachers of norms and values. What is so heartbreaking is that these celebs and influencers are everywhere on social media teaching bad behaviours. They smoke marijuana and advocate for its legalisation in their Instagram photos and videos. They abuse alcohol and swallow the blue and green pills in their snapchat videos. Some of them have been seen dissolving methamphetamine in drinks in some online videos. Yet, these are the people our children regard as role models. The danger is when favourite celebrities, influencers or showbiz idols participate in deviant behaviours online, they begin to standardize such deviant action as appropriate, (*Guardian* 2023 n. p)

Indeed, social media glamorizes drugs and alcohol, and it is easy to see why. For instance, it is common to find alcohol-related posts of youth on Instagram and Facebook portray alcohol in a positive social context. Not only are the average young adults posting pictures of themselves with fancy alcoholic drinks or out drinking with friends, but celebrities are doing it too. Instagram especially has long been criticized as being a highlight reel and a lead cause of FOMO (fear of missing out). When the rich and famous are posting luxurious pictures of themselves with a drink in hand, it is easy to get caught up in the idea that these substances are needed to have a good time, encouraging people to give it a try themselves. With these entrenched, socially-oriented activities such as social media use can be associated with a greater likelihood of lifetime alcohol use and past drunkenness.

Taken together, evidence is continually emerging on the associations between increased social media use and increased use of alcohol and other drugs. However, while researchers have successfully strung a relationship between social media use and drug abuse, it is perhaps more heartwarming to note that the social media equally hold great promise in the war against drug abuse in Nigeria. Globally, citizen engagement in the fight against substance abuse is in vogue, and social media have emerged a potent instrument to help publicize the dangers of drug abuse and engender greater public participation and advocacy. Scholars and policy makers have increasingly advocated engaging citizens more substantially in the fight against drug misuse and it is thought that such collaboration could win the drug war.

Against this backdrop, this paper attempts to determine the extent to which the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) and the National Agency for Food, Drug, Administration and Control (NAFDAC) - two agencies tasked

with the responsibility of stemming the tide of drug abuse in Nigeria - are engaging with citizens via social media, in their bid to win the War Against Drug Abuse (WADA).

Statement of the Problem

There is no gainsaying the fact that Nigeria has a drug problem. Often, if not daily, the Nigeria media are awash with fresh reports of the arrest of drug traffickers and seizures of illicit substances by operatives of the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA). And this has been consistent for about a decade or so. In fact, the United Nations Office on Drug and Crime (UNODC) in Nigeria reported in 2022 that around 14.4% (14.3 million) of people aged 15 and 64 years abuse drugs. This figure was higher than the global average at the time. The dust had barely settled when the NDLEA in 2023 raised the alarm in the *Guardian* that 40 percent of Nigerian youths, between 18 and 35, are deeply involved in the abuse of drugs, and blamed the social media for it. The Nigerian government in collaboration with the agency has initiated several approaches to combat the drug menace, including television talk shows, media documentaries and the launch of the War Against Drug Abuse (WADA) in 2021. It is not clear to what extent these initiatives have been effective, particularly with the NDLEA reporting recently that a significant percentage of the population was still involved in drug use.

Where radio campaigns and television documentaries were once relied upon as the major avenues to bring to bear the ills of drug abuse, social media platforms have now brought new opportunities for anti-narcotic institutions to interact with citizens and push for participatory advocacy. It is estimated that on a given day, 50% of Facebook's 500-million plus users log-on to social networking sites. The average user is connected to 80 community pages, groups, and events, and creates about 90 pieces of content for posting each month. Twitter's 200 million users are also thought to produce around 110 million tweets per day on topics ranging from celebrity gossips, food, drinks, breaking news about disasters, developments, technology and innovations. Factoring in equally engaging platforms like WhatsApp, Instagram, and YouTube equates the masses. What is important to note is that millions of people all over the world are constantly sharing an extremely wide range of fascinating, quirky, funny, irrelevant and important contents all at once. Given that social media plays such an integral part in our life, the question arises: which social media platforms are the NDLEA and NAFDAC using to engage the public in their bid to win the drug war? How are they using the platforms? And to what extent are Nigerian citizens engaging with these agencies using social media?

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

- (i) ascertain the depth of social media penetration in Nigeria,
- (ii) ascertain the extent to which the NDLEA and NAFDAC deploy social media in the fight against drug abuse,
- (iii) find out the extent to which the NDLEA and NAFDAC and the Nigerian public engage each other in the social media.

Conceptual Review of Literature

Social Media and Youths

Social media refers to a computer-based technology that promotes the sharing of ideas, thoughts and information through virtual networks and communities. The first decade of the new millennium witnessed a new quality of the social impact of digitization. It was the birth of social media. With platforms like Facebook (founded 2004) and Twitter (2006), the conditions of the sundry aspects of human communication have been fundamentally transformed. What is called social media is subsumed under web 2.0. The concept is used to describe the second stage of the Internet, characterized by the change from static web pages to dynamic or user-generated content and the growth of social networks. Web 2.0 refers to web pages that emphasize ease of use, interaction, greater citizen engagement, participatory culture and interoperability for end users.

Social media includes individual formats like blogs and podcasts, usually operated by a person or an organization, as well as collective formats like social network sites (SNS, for example Facebook), Microblogging services (for example, Twitter), video and photography platforms (for example, YouTube, Instagram) and wikis (for example, Wikipedia), where a great number of networked users collaborate within a single service. More than 4.7 billion people use social media, equal to roughly 60% of the world's population (Dollarhide, 2023). Today, social media messaging apps and platforms are the most commonly used sites worldwide. The majority in almost all the social networking sites are youths. Mayo Clinic says a 2018 Pew Research Center survey of nearly 750 13-17 year olds found that at least 75% have at least one social media profile, 45% are online almost constantly, two thirds are online almost nine hours a day, and use social media platforms, such as Tiktok, Youtube, Facebook, Instagram or Snapchat. Another 2018 report by Hopelab and Well Being Trust found that 93% of youths aged 14-22 used social media daily. Indeed, social media plays a big role in teens' culture today, but the potential risks are equally enormous.

Drug Abuse

There is no doubt that humans require and use drugs to improve their general well-being. However, when drugs are misused, it becomes an abuse. Drug abuse, therefore, refers to the use of certain chemicals for the purpose of creating pleasurable effects on the brain. It is the harmful or hazardous use of psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs. Drug abuse is also known as substance abuse. It is defined as the harmful intake of drugs in ways or quantities hazardous to them or people around them, or both. Common examples of substances that are usually abused include sedatives, alcohol, heroin, marijuana (ganja), tobacco, bhang, hashish (charas), different types of cough syrups, brown sugar, and cocaine, opium, cannabinoids, amphetamines and hypnotics. Anxiolytics and other stimulants like caffeine, hallucinogens, nicotine, volatile solvents and phencyclidine are also classified as psychoactive substances, among others. Drug abuse has serious negative consequences on the individual, economy and society at large.

Netizens, Social Media and Drug Abuse

This paper has established that social media is a big part of the lives of many young adults. But in reality, people of all ages and demography use social media, as it complements many parts of our lives. Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and many other social networking sites allow users to share and interact with online contents and to connect with like-minded people. However, for the unsuspecting youth, there are a variety of risk factors in social media use, and there is a clear connection between social media use and substance abuse. A survey cited by the Washington Post found that teenagers who regularly use popular social media outlets were more likely to drink, use drugs, and smoke than their peers who do not. Specifically, they were found to be three times more likely to drink and twice as likely to use marijuana. While social media platforms do not directly lead to drug use, certain posts, photos, or people on social media can trigger it, or put pressure on teens to drink and try drugs (Turnbridge, 2021). An Elsevier (2017) Editorial sums up the point.

In addition, by seeing friends and family out having fun “all the time” on social media, young viewers may feel a greater need to do these things themselves. They may develop that “fear of missing out,” and feel tempted to try more risky behaviors like substance use, in attempts to look cool or fit in. This is another common cause of teen drug use today. Social media is filled with instances of substance use, whether its pictures of parties, someone smoking in a joint, or direct messages with drug dealers. Substance use is rampant and often glorified by celebrities and others on social media. There have been reports of social

media being used as a strategy for selling drugs, with hashtags facilitating the process of pairing buyers with sellers. Tobacco, electronic cigarette, and alcohol industries have widely integrated social media platforms into marketing strategies that are fully accessible to teens. In this way social media has opened up doors for these industries to market to youth even when direct marketing to minors is against the law or supposed to be internally regulated. The burgeoning cannabis industry is opening up even more opportunities for teens to have exposure to advertising through social media. Exposure to substance use imagery is associated with subsequent onset in use, which is why drinking alcohol and using drugs in movies warrants an R-rating. Social media is harder to regulate.

A 2011 report by the National Center on Addiction and Substance Abuse at Columbia University showed that teens who use social media were more likely to use tobacco, alcohol, and marijuana than teens who do not use social media, and risk was higher for those who had seen pictures of kids using or passed out from alcohol or drugs. Another study found that undergraduate students with disordered online social networking use were more likely to have problematic drinking and difficulties with emotional regulation. Furthermore, the same study takes this area of inquiry by demonstrating a pathway from social media use to increased drinking. Their finding that peer injunctive norms serve as a mediator between social media exposure and the initiation of drinking behaviors points toward intervention targets of peer influence and normative behaviors.

One way social media tend to promote substance use is by glamorizing drug and alcohol. Not only are the average young adults posting pictures of themselves with fancy alcoholic drinks or out drinking with friends, but celebrities are doing it too. By constantly showing famous influencers using these substances, it glorifies smoking marijuana or the use of other substances. *Netizens* tend to be impressionable as a community, and if they see a so-called celebrity light one up a stick of cigarette, they figure — why not us too? Second, social media sites have become a large part of people's daily lives, especially when it comes to teenagers and young adults. Some people will spend hours a day scrolling through pictures on Instagram or making their next video on TikTok with the hopes that one will go viral. While the goal of these platforms is to have fun, provide entertainment, and to get people socializing online, so much screen time could be having unforeseen consequences. In such moments, pop up and blink advertisements featuring drugs and narcotics could change the narrative altogether. With these sites only growing in popularity and

number, the connection between social media and substance abuse looks no idle speculation. One study found that teens who use social media are more likely to use tobacco, alcohol, and marijuana than their peers who do not. The relationship between drinking and social media is especially alarming. Greater alcohol-related social media engagement is correlated with higher rates of self-reported drinking problems as well as alcohol use disorders. Even scarier is that exposure to friends' alcohol-related social media content could actually predict the onset of drinking in adolescents (Moreno, Hanneke, Bas Van Den, Gebhardt, 2018).

Though social media platforms often market themselves as some fun, safe places to connect with peers and family, the dark reality is that they are connecting users in a very troubling way, and these negative influences could be fuelling negative addictions. A case in point is when substance abuse is glorified by celebrities and others on social media platforms - they promote substance use and encourage people to give it a try themselves.

Social Media Reach vs. Engagement: the Nexus

Reach in social media metric and analytics measure how many people have seen a given post – how many people it has reached. Post Engagement Rate is the ratio of interactions with a social media post to the total number of followers the page or profile has. This metric shows how involved followers are with the content posted on a social media page. Generally, higher Post Engagement Rate shows higher levels of followers involvement. Engagement, therefore measures the number of interactions made with your post – how views, clicks, comments, likes, & shares your post gets. However, no matter the number of clicks and or comments a post attracts, if no real efforts are made to respond to comments made by way of inquiries many, questions, posers or speculations, 'no real engagement could be said to have taken place between the source and the followers. It is the reason all such interactive platforms are collectively tagged 'social' media (Bradshaw and Rohumaa, 2011).

That is why reach and engagement do not go hand in hand. High reach doesn't necessarily mean that your engagement is high as well – it's possible to have high reach with low engagement and vice versa. It is one thing to create compelling social media posts with great appeal, but pages and handles with high citizen engagement would retain greater loyalty, higher visibility, higher reach and a dedicated follow-base. Engaging citizens through response to User Generated Contents (UGC) and timely engagements hold the key to greater visibility and reach.

Overview of the NDLEA and WADA

A post on the official website of the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) reveals that the organization is a federal law enforcement Agency established by Decree No. 48 of 29th December 1989. The promulgation of the decree was chiefly in response to the rising trend in the demand for and trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances which adversely affected the international image of Nigerians and Nigeria in the 1980s. Since then the trafficking of illicit substances has become an organized criminal activity that undermines the security and development of the country and therefore demands urgent attention and priority from the government. The establishment of the organization was aimed at exterminating illicit drug trafficking and consumption in the Nigerian society. It also targets any involved in drugs, especially their importation, exportation, sale, transfer, purchase, cultivation, manufacture, extraction and possession.

NDLEA is in charge of drug policy and control in Nigeria. Within this purview, the Agency has the mandate to curtail illicit production, importation, exportation, sale and trafficking of psychoactive substances. Employees of NDLEA carry out interdiction and destruction of narcotic drugs and other illicit substances. They also engage in preventive drug abuse activities such as advocacy and counseling, and rehabilitation of drug users.

In fulfilling the mandate of the Agency, thousands of experts narcotic operatives and well-trained support staff of NDLEA work across Nigeria with a visible presence at international airports, seaports, border crossing and major highways. Committed to keeping society safe from the dangers of illicit substances and their purveyors, NDLEA operatives are actively engaged in the tracking, arrest and prosecution of traffickers of dangerous substances under the various relevant drug laws of Nigeria.

NDLEA has 14 directorates, 14 zonal commands, 111 state area commands and 10 Special (airports & seaports) commands. Its operatives are present in all the nation's airports, seaports, border posts and strategic locations on the road networks in the country. The body has a string of ongoing campaigns two of which are the Offensive Action and War Against drug Abuse (WADA). The Offensive Action is a non-stop, ramped-up drug supply reduction campaign. Launched on 18th January 2021, it galvanised NDLEA operatives to work round the clock in seamless, coordinated, goal-oriented actions that include tracking and arresting of drug traffickers, interdiction of illicit substance

shipments and fast-track prosecution of offenders. The War Against Drug Abuse (WADA) is an advocacy campaign launched on 26th June 2021 by President Muhammadu Buhari to create awareness that will suffuse society with anti-drug culture. It entails setting up coordinated anti-drug committees at States, LGAs and communities across the federation.

The agency lists as its vision the task of becoming the most proactive and leading Drug Law Enforcement Agency in Africa and one of the best in the world and contributes to the creation and maintenance of a positive image for Nigeria. It says it will achieve this by deploying all resources at its disposal for the total eradication of illicit trafficking in narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances, by cutting off the supply of illicit drugs and bringing suppliers to book, reducing the demand for illicit drugs and other substances of abuse and tracing and recovering drug-related proceeds, through effective drug law enforcement.

Overview of NAFDAC

The National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) was established by Decree No. 15 of 1993 as amended by Decree No. 19 of 1999 and now the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control Act Cap N1 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria (LFN) 2004 to regulate and control the manufacturing, importation, exportation, distribution, advertisement, sale and use of Food, Drugs, Cosmetics, Medical Devices, Packaged Water, Chemicals and Detergents (collectively known as regulated products). The agency was officially established in October 1992.

The NAFDAC's organization consists of the Director General's Office and fourteen (14) directorates overseeing a string of functions performed by the agency, including its oversight on drugs and narcotics. The Drug and Evaluation Directorate says it develops, operates and continually improves QMS {QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM} ensure a robust and effective inspection operation that will guarantee safe, effective and good quality medicinal products, cosmetics & allied products, while the Narcotics & Controlled Substances Directorate grants authorization for the import and export of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances as well as other controlled substances.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is anchored on the Theory of Citizen Participation. Effective citizen engagement is generally accepted as one of the most important steps towards making science and technology meaningful to the public. Citizen participation is a process which provides private individuals an opportunity to influence public decisions and has long been a component of the democratic decision making process. The roots of this theory can be traced to ancient Greece and colonial New England. Cogan and Sharpe (1986, p. 283) say citizen participation was institutionalized in the mid-1960s and that government processes and procedures were designed to facilitate external participation.

Proponents of the theory had argued that it was counterproductive for agencies, both public and private to minimize public participation in planning efforts claiming citizen participation was too expensive and time consuming. Making a case for greater citizen participation programmes, they contend that there are tangible benefits that can be derived from an effective citizen participation programme. Cogan and Sharpe (1986, p. 284) have identified five benefits of citizen engagement: information and ideas on public issues, public support for planning decisions, avoidance of protracted conflicts and costly delays, reservoir of goodwill which can carry over to future decisions, and spirit of cooperation and trust between an agency and the public.

Since then, several adaptations, ferments and extensions have evolved. One school of thought says citizen participation should not be an end in itself, but a unique ingredient in the overall goal. This position has tended to be popularized by proponents who see far reaching prospects in science-public engagement. Bringing development via science, innovation and technology to the public is one of the main pillars of the welfare State, and one good that has the capacity to better human living. Without citizen engagement, these prospects are unrealizable, for as the authors note, citizens are increasingly expected to take a more participatory role in society, which increases the need for them to be knowledgeable about a wide range of uncertain risks and to properly prepare themselves in case those risks become reality.

Methodology

To address the research objectives, the study relied on literature searches to determine the status of social media depth in Nigeria. The researchers then conducted a qualitative content analysis of the social media handles, accounts and pages of the NDLEA and NAFDAC for a period of six months, spanning January 1, 2023 - June 30, 2023. The content analysis helped ascertain the

deployment or otherwise of the social media by these organizations in their campaigns against drug and substance abuse in Nigeria. The units of analysis included the agencies' anti-drug abuse media pages, accounts and handles containing interactive features, hyperlinks, audience traffic features, as well as video and sound click analytics. While the researchers acknowledge the existence of a trove of social media platforms, this study was based on the agencies' presence and citizen engagements on Facebook, Twitter, YouTube and Instagram. Where an agency has its WhatsApp contact linked to a webpage, this was given a mention.

Findings, Analysis and Discussion

Data analysed in this section and the discussions are based on the research questions of the study. Whether to follow friends, family, acquaintances, or celebrities and people in the art and entertainment industry, stay in touch with developments, or seek out medical diagnoses, social media usage in Nigeria has been on the rise in recent years. For most users, the aim is to keep in touch with close relations. Therefore, it is not surprising that WhatsApp is the most used social media platform in the country. As of the third quarter of 2021, this instant messaging and voice-over-IP platform was used by nearly 92 percent of Nigeria's overall Internet users, ahead of Facebook and Instagram. However, Facebook was the most preferred platform for the majority of individuals accessing the news on social media, (Sasa 2002).

Social media diffusion and use is consequent upon Internet user penetration in any given society. Sasa has mapped a trajectory of Internet use in Nigeria since 2018 (28.75%), 2019 (33.42%), 2020 (34.55%), 2021 (36.67%), of which about 33 million are active users. According to the author, men constitute the most active population group (58.3%), with 18-34 years old. As of January 2022, Nigeria with a projected population of well over 200 million had 32.9 million active social media users. WhatsApp retained its place as the most popular platform used in the country, with over 90 million users. Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram followed as the most used social media platforms in Nigeria, (Sasa, 2022).

Compared to many Nigerian agencies, the NDLEA has a burgeoning Internet presence that gives life to her social media communications. A simple click on the agency's official website ushers users into the full complement of their web 2.0 presence, namely, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and YouTube, an email address, as well as links to its Directorate of Media and Advocacy. Going by information available on the site, the directorate is headed by Mr Femi Babafemi and has five functions, Inter Alia.

Coordination of media coverage for all activities of the Agency, including organising press briefings and interviews, appearances on radio/TV programmes, and issuing press releases on the operations of the Agency and its leadership; coverage of court trials of suspects; production of documentaries, editorials and advocacy materials; coordinating internal events/programmes, courtesy/advocacy visits; handling inter-agency liaison; and facilitating public enlightenment through media and other public platforms; Facilitating engagement between NDLEA and its followers (especially youths) on social media platforms; Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter and YouTube(emphasis mine).

It is safe to submit that the agency uses these platforms fairly optimally in engaging with citizens and bringing its programmes, activities and the ills of substance abuse to Nigerians. However, visitors to NDLEA’s website are treated to too few (if any) interactive pop ups and hyperlinks containing video and soundbites. Anyone who desires to have a feel of the activities of the organisation will have to click on the social media icons at the bottom of the site and be redirected to the individual social media platforms of the agency.

NDLEA’s Facebook account is yet to be verified. However, on Facebook alone, NDLEA boasts a relatively modest following of about 159, 000 users on an account that permits instant real time toll free call and messaging. In context however, in a country seriously grappling with drug related issues, and a Facebook user depth of nearly 41.6 million as of May 2023, (Statista, 2023), this looks grossly underwhelming. That figure accounts for 18.5 percent of Nigeria’s population. Overall, two age groups accounted for 32.2 percent of users: those between the ages of 18 and 24, and those between the ages of 18 and 34, making these two groups the largest age groups of Facebook users in the country. Instructively, this is the same age bracket which the NDLEA found to be” deeply involved in the abuse of drugs” in the report carried by the *Guardian* of May 10, 2023 entitled “Social Media and our Drug Problem” by Philemon Akwu.

Between January 1 and June 30, 2023, the NDLEA has made well over 170 Facebook posts bothering on its Weekly Interactive Forum on Twitter Space, Open Forum, Seminars, Webinars, Scam Alerts, Arrests and Testimonials of Repentant Drug Users – all complete with audio clicks, videos and links. Videos have an average of 1,500 views, individual posts have hundreds of ‘likes, but comments on supposedly engaging contents like “It Concerns Us All” (Feb. 20) and “World Drug Day Alert: Dangers of Nitrous Ballonsare

typically few and engagement with the public by way of response to user generated content and question in comment section are none existent. One would have thought that while the Open Forum broadcast of June 16, 2023 was being aired, someone should have been manning the Facebook handle and also responding by way of comments. Till this minute, not one of the questions raised by followers has been responded to. Again, what would make NDLEA's Weekly Interactive Forum (June 21, 2023) really interactive is two way transactional communication and sharing of meaning. But as in other such forums, none of the questions raised were answered or responded to, even the one by one Chinedu Ugwute-Chiemezie, who asked "Please do you have drug addicts rehab centre in Ebony state? If yes, please I want to know the address." This seeming oversight is seriously disturbing and the agency risks talking all to itself. Facebook posts on their own are a linear form of communication, and engaging followers makes for effective, transactional communication.

NDLEA joined YouTube in April 2021 and has about 1.27k subscribers, 183 videos and 53,314 cumulative viewing hours. What is lacking in NDLEA's YouTube experience is real dialogue with viewers, as is the case with its Facebook account. Videos are just streamed with little recourse to the concerns of viewers. This calls for immediate action. The organization has an official Instagram account with 51.9 followers and 2, 793 posts to date. The contents found on the organization's Facebook account are syndicated to its Instagram, YouTube and Twitter handles, but again, audience engagements remain low.

NAFDAC has a verified Facebook page and despite the account being in existence since March 2011, it has just 48,000 followers. In the period of this study, the agency has made a about 125 posts on Facebook. Aside the posts which serve mainly the purpose of information, the agency has no meaningful engagement with the public queries and questions in comment section are hardly responded to and enquiries are typically not given a reply. A case in point is the agency's Public Alert No. 022/2023 about an unwholesome Sprite 50cl glass bottle batch number AZ6 22:23 made nearly a week ago. Till the time of this report, not a single response was made in response to the numerous questions from citizens. The agency has a presence on Instagram where it has around 26, 000 followers and has made 221 posts to date. It is on Youtube @NAFDACNIGERIA with 664 subscribers and 185 videos. However, comments are typically few and audience engagements barely exist.

Conclusion/Recommendations

The last decade has completely re-shaped the way in which we communicate. It has become clear that Internet-based communication is growing and all fields of life have to adapt to its use, including agencies spearheading the ongoing global onslaught against drug and substance abuse. Social media engagement forms a large part of Internet-based communication, and plays a crucial role in all areas of human endeavours. Even though specific platforms will continue to evolve, the concept of social media is likely to stay. This holds great promise both in bringing to the fore, the ills of illicit drug use, and in engaging youths and the Nigerian public in the war against drug abuse. But to achieve this, Nigerian anti-narcotic agencies will have to go beyond simply acting as purveyors of information on social media into real citizen engagements, in order to engender a participatory advocacy and onslaught against the menace. Since drug abuse and substance users reside with the people, it is safe to conclude that no meaningful solution or remediation can be achieved without people-media integration and participation. Social media fits that bill, and by far.

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